

System Dynamics Based Model

D4.3

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2. Background Information

Table 1: Technical information.

Project Full title	Rural regeneration through systemic heritage-led strategies	
Project Acronym	RURITAGE	
Grant Agreement No.	776465	
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Table 2: List of abbreviations.

CNH	Cultural and Natural Heritage
D	Deliverable
GPI	Global Performance Indicator
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
R/Rs/ARs	Replicator/Replicators/Additional Replicators
RHH	Rural Heritage Hub
RM	Role Model
SIA	Systemic Innovation Area
SD	System Dynamics
WP	Work Package
XMILE	OASIS XML Interchange Language (XMILE) for System Dynamics

3. Summary

System Dynamics (SD) modelling applied to heritage-led rural regeneration is one of the key points of the RURITAGE project. Work Package 4 focuses on the Monitoring System, in which the SD modelling is a central piece. Task 4.4 tackles the introductory works to design a final solution within the framework of the Monitoring System.

The report begins with an update of the situation on the development of the Monitoring Platform, since many changes have occurred in the last stages of the project that have influenced the platform.

The following section describes the SD model building, included detailed information about the analysis of the monitoring data, and the identification of dynamics relationships. A brief description of the process to evaluate the relevance of every KPI is provided. To complete the explanation of the process, the design of the sub-systems and the construction of the matrix that correlates the SIAs and the KPIs are described. The last part of the section provides the system design and the models architecture, including a screenshot of the user interface and the explanation of the main characteristics and available simulation options for the end-user.

The report ends up with a conclusions section, containing the main outcomes and some ideas for further research and development in this field.

4. Introduction

The technique of System Dynamics (SD) modelling and simulation is not presently widely adopted within rural areas. Where applied, SD modelling has had considerable impact on practical issues in the areas of management, urban planning and environmental change, to mention a few, but its practical impact has been less than might be expected, particularly in addressing social concerns. SD is at present an expert discipline that is the domain of people with subject matter expertise. This is partly due to the skills and knowledge required to use system dynamics tools, partly due to significant licensing costs of software and, finally, partly due to lack of awareness.

Based on the previous statements, RURITAGE faces the challenge to test and demonstrate the potential usefulness of SD modelling and make easier the access to SD techniques and tools, especially for rural areas and policy makers, so that they better appreciate the complex dynamics of cultural and natural heritage and human systems, and then, use those insights in a constructive way to foster heritage-led rural regeneration.

The deliverable D4.3 “*System Dynamics Based Model*” in RURITAGE project belongs to the category OTHER, that is, the model itself is the deliverable, but this written report tries to shed light to the process and technicalities involved in the development of the SD models. For further details on the use and results of the SD models, please see deliverable D4.4 “*Rural Regeneration Activities: data, results, conclusions and recommendations*”.

5. Monitoring Platform: Updated Description

Since the deliverable D4.2 was released, a series of changes have been applied to the Monitoring Platform. Some of those changes are related to the new functionality of System Dynamics modelling, but some others are included to adapt to new requirements and project evolution. For this reason, this deliverable includes this section with an updated description of the platform.

5.1 Development Framework : Mongo, Nginx, Flask, Gunicorn and Python

The monitoring platform described in deliverable D4.2 has been implemented in six Replicators (Rs) around Europe and nine Additional Replicators (ARs) including ENP countries and beyond, as shown in Figure 1. This monitoring platform provides from global performance values, i.e., GPI, to detailed KPI data. The chosen tools were been *MongoDB* [1] as NoSQL database software and *Grafana* [2] to build the dashboards, since it is an open source metric analytic and visualisation suite, most commonly used for visualising time series data, able to work with multiple data stores. It supports many different storage backends for time series data (data source). Each data source has a specific query editor customised for the features and capabilities that the particular data source sets out. *Grafana* also allows data from multiple data sources to be combined on a single dashboard. Some additional functionalities have been developed using *Flask* [3], python, javascript and *Bootstrap* [4].

Figure 1: Location of Role Models and Replicators participating in RURITAGE (© RURITAGE).

There are several tools for the development of SD models, some free or open source and others proprietary. For an extensive comparison, general purpose, please see Wikipedia¹. For the purposes of RURITAGE, a very helpful description and analysis of tools was found in the [PoliRURAL project](#). Specifically, deliverable [D3.3 “System Dynamics Tool Technical Specifications”](#) includes a very useful overview of available software implementations for SD modelling. For RURITAGE project we have selected *sd.js*, a javascript library that allows a smooth integration of developed SD models into the already deployed Monitoring Platform.

6. System Dynamics Model Building

System Dynamics (SD) modelling applied to heritage-led rural regeneration is one of the results of the RURITAGE project. Work Package 4 have focused on the Monitoring System, in which the SD model is a key piece.

The model building process has followed several phases including: (i) monitoring data analysis and identification of the main dynamics relationships; (iii) design of a structure of sub-systems; and (iv) system’s design. This process has given a conceptual and structural background for the first attempt at creating the SD models.

6.1 Monitoring Data Analysis and Identification of Dynamics Relationships

The analysis of the data provided by the Rs through the Monitoring Platform has been performed in the form of a matrix that shows the relevance of each KPI for the different SIAs. The first step is to study the importance of every indicator according to the expert knowledge and has been performed through OWA sensitivity analysis. The second step is the matching of the data collected from the pilots with the information obtained from the previous task. That information can be seen in the matrix of KPIs-SIAs assignment. The last step is the

¹ There are different software packages on the market, usable on PC's, to write concise instructions so that the computer interprets the system to study [[Comparison of system dynamics software - Wikipedia](#)]. They all have a great deal in common: the available functions and default graphical presentations are similar. VENSIM is very strong in terms of capacity, performance and functionality. It provides a PLE (Personal Learning Edition) license quite flexible in the appearance of the model diagram, and contains a set of analysis tools that use the structure of the model to present information to quickly find problems and investigate sources of behaviour.

abstraction, or generalisation, of identified key points, in order to be able to face general situation and not only those that are similar to the ones used to build the model. This refers to the topics included into the series of tables from **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** to **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.**

6.1.1 OWA Sensitivity Analysis

In group decision making processes, and usually in the presence of conflicting goals, the idea of trade-offs corresponds to viewing the global evaluation of an action as lying within the worst and best ratings. OWA (Ordered Weighted Averaging) operators [5] can realize trade-offs between objectives by allowing a positive compensation between ratings, i.e., a higher degree of satisfaction of one of the criteria can compensate for a lower degree of satisfaction of another criterion to a certain extent [6].

In RURITAGE project, every participating expert has provided an influence value for the KPIs. In some cases, e.g., CC-01, all the experts more or less agree about the Influence value assigned to the indicator. In other cases, e.g., CC-02, there are significant differences among the experts' evaluations. An OWA operator is used to aggregate all the answers. Thus, an OWA-modified weight is assigned to each indicator, where higher values means that most of the experts consider the KPI is among the most important, while lower values means that experts consider the KPI is not so important.

The Table 3 shows the relevance of each KPI, taking into account the different criteria expressed by the experts. Specifically, in this analysis, the OWA operator uses the RIM (Regular Increasing Monotone) quantifier. The highest result indicates the most important KPI, taking into account the specific criteria. It is thus possible to see at a glance which are the most and also the least relevant indicators.

The sensitivity analysis illustrated in this Section shows the effect of the *orness* parameter in the weights and rankings, i.e., setting the relevance of the indicators. Higher *orness* values give more importance to the highest weights in a more conservative approach, while lower values promote the lowest weights, trying to soften the discrepancy among experts. According to this, *orness* = 0.5 gives the same importance to all the values, so it produces an arithmetic mean. In this case, the sensitivity analysis also shows that some indicators always have either high or low ranking positions, despite the *orness* value; so it is possible to group the KPIs in three sets {*high, medium, low*} according to their relevance (last column in the series of tables from Table 3 to Table 8). See the full process description for every KPI in [7].

Table 3: Sensitivity analysis of the Orness effect on Cultural Capital indicators' weights and rankings.

Code	<i>Orness</i> = 0.1		<i>Orness</i> = 0.4		<i>Orness</i> = 0.5		<i>Orness</i> = 0.6		<i>Orness</i> = 0.9		Relevance
	Weight	Ranking									
CC-01	17.44%	3	16.03%	1	15.01%	2	14.05%	3	11.89%	3	high
CC-02	5.79%	6	7.26%	8	7.65%	8	8.00%	8	8.74%	7	med
CC-03	2.23%	9	4.03%	9	4.58%	9	5.05%	9	6.06%	9	low
CC-04	1.75%	10	2.25%	10	2.69%	10	3.17%	10	4.46%	10	low
CC-05	1.54%	11	1.99%	11	2.28%	11	2.58%	11	3.31%	11	low
CC-06a	18.66%	2	15.79%	2	15.42%	1	15.22%	1	15.13%	1	high
CC-06b	19.98%	1	15.74%	3	14.90%	3	14.28%	2	13.20%	2	high
CC-07	5.49%	8	7.27%	7	7.71%	7	8.04%	7	8.57%	8	med
CC-08	10.65%	5	11.06%	4	11.15%	4	11.17%	4	11.09%	4	med
CC-09	10.79%	4	9.79%	5	9.53%	5	9.29%	5	8.76%	6	med
CC-10	5.68%	7	8.79%	6	9.08%	6	9.14%	6	8.79%	5	med

Table 4: Sensitivity analysis of the Orness effect on Natural Capital indicators' weights and rankings.

Code	<i>Orness</i> = 0.1		<i>Orness</i> = 0.4		<i>Orness</i> = 0.5		<i>Orness</i> = 0.6		<i>Orness</i> = 0.9		Relevance
	Weight	Ranking									
NC-01	45.29%	1	26.36%	1	23.59%	1	21.49%	1	17.55%	1	high
NC-02	5.91%	6	9.40%	6	10.21%	6	10.80%	6	11.76%	5	low
NC-03	8.79%	5	13.54%	3	13.54%	3	13.39%	3	12.74%	3	med
NC-04	4.47%	8	7.67%	7	8.64%	7	9.33%	7	10.41%	7	low
NC-05	10.12%	3	11.83%	4	11.68%	4	11.46%	4	10.78%	6	med
NC-06	4.48%	7	5.46%	8	6.39%	8	7.40%	8	10.08%	8	low
NC-07	11.89%	2	15.52%	2	15.25%	2	14.99%	2	14.49%	2	high
NC-08	9.06%	4	10.21%	5	10.70%	5	11.15%	5	12.20%	4	med

Table 5: Sensitivity analysis of the Orness effect on Built Capital indicators' weights and rankings.

Code	<i>Orness</i> = 0.1		<i>Orness</i> = 0.4		<i>Orness</i> = 0.5		<i>Orness</i> = 0.6		<i>Orness</i> = 0.9		Relevance
	Weight	Ranking									
BC-01	1.37%	15	2.88%	14	3.42%	14	3.87%	14	4.77%	14	low
BC-02	0.96%	16	1.23%	16	1.49%	16	1.78%	16	2.58%	15	low
BC-03	1.56%	14	1.90%	15	1.90%	15	1.89%	15	1.86%	16	low
BC-04	6.59%	6	5.64%	12	5.66%	12	5.75%	11	6.18%	11	low
BC-05	5.32%	11	5.00%	13	5.13%	13	5.29%	13	5.74%	12	low
BC-06	13.62%	2	9.56%	2	8.96%	2	8.50%	2	7.61%	5	high
BC-07	13.79%	1	10.02%	1	9.32%	1	8.77%	1	7.66%	4	high
BC-08	8.43%	4	8.07%	5	7.91%	5	7.74%	5	7.31%	7	high
BC-09	6.28%	7	5.83%	10	5.75%	11	5.69%	12	5.61%	13	med
BC-10	5.52%	10	6.58%	8	6.59%	8	6.52%	9	6.18%	10	med
BC-11	6.27%	8	7.00%	7	7.29%	7	7.46%	6	7.55%	6	med
BC-12	9.00%	3	8.67%	3	8.50%	3	8.29%	3	7.69%	3	high
BC-13	6.20%	9	6.02%	9	6.14%	10	6.28%	10	6.66%	8	med
BC-14	3.28%	13	5.76%	11	6.37%	9	6.92%	8	8.24%	1	med
BC-15a	8.05%	5	8.48%	4	8.28%	4	8.10%	4	7.74%	2	high
BC-15b	3.75%	12	7.37%	6	7.31%	6	7.15%	7	6.63%	9	med

Table 6: Sensitivity analysis of the Orness effect on Social Capital indicators' weights and rankings.

Code	<i>Orness</i> = 0.1		<i>Orness</i> = 0.4		<i>Orness</i> = 0.5		<i>Orness</i> = 0.6		<i>Orness</i> = 0.9		Relevance
	Weight	Ranking									
SC-01a	23.14%	2	17.25%	2	16.33%	2	15.62%	2	14.30%	2	high
SC-01b	23.18%	1	19.47%	1	19.15%	1	18.98%	1	18.80%	1	high
SC-02	6.48%	5	10.51%	3	10.99%	3	11.24%	3	11.46%	3	high
SC-03	11.70%	3	10.38%	4	10.09%	4	9.87%	4	9.44%	5	med
SC-04	5.27%	8	8.35%	6	8.70%	6	8.91%	6	9.12%	6	med
SC-05a	3.52%	10	4.95%	9	5.28%	9	5.52%	9	5.92%	9	low
SC-05b	5.79%	6	7.55%	7	7.46%	7	7.29%	8	6.79%	8	med
SC-06a	4.11%	9	4.80%	10	5.02%	10	5.25%	10	5.83%	10	low
SC-06b	5.48%	7	7.14%	8	7.38%	8	7.56%	7	7.91%	7	low
SC-07	11.33%	4	9.60%	5	9.61%	5	9.76%	5	10.43%	4	med

Table 7: Sensitivity analysis of the Orness effect on Human Capital indicators' weights and rankings.

Code	<i>Orness</i> = 0.1		<i>Orness</i> = 0.4		<i>Orness</i> = 0.5		<i>Orness</i> = 0.6		<i>Orness</i> = 0.9		Relevance
	Weight	Ranking									
HC-01	21.89%	1	19.52%	1	18.63%	1	18.02%	1	17.18%	1	high
HC-02	6.51%	8	7.70%	8	8.39%	8	8.95%	8	9.98%	7	low
HC-03	7.94%	6	9.52%	6	10.36%	5	11.05%	5	12.33%	3	med
HC-04	12.42%	4	11.75%	4	11.65%	4	11.59%	4	11.48%	4	med
HC-05	17.53%	2	14.24%	2	13.70%	2	13.28%	2	12.48%	2	high
HC-06	7.55%	7	10.37%	5	10.03%	6	9.72%	7	9.08%	8	low
HC-07	14.41%	3	13.57%	3	12.81%	3	12.12%	3	10.60%	6	high
HC-08	8.51%	5	9.09%	7	9.62%	7	10.02%	6	10.70%	5	med
HC-09	3.23%	9	4.24%	9	4.80%	9	5.26%	9	6.17%	9	low

Table 8: Sensitivity analysis of the Orness effect on Financial Capital indicators' weights and rankings.

Code	Orness = 0.1		Orness = 0.4		Orness = 0.5		Orness = 0.6		Orness = 0.9		Relevance
	Weight	Ranking									
FC-01	7.66%	6	11.68%	5	12.63%	5	13.55%	5	15.93%	4	low
FC-02	17.75%	3	18.82%	3	18.19%	3	17.64%	3	16.44%	3	med
FC-03	10.26%	5	9.67%	6	10.27%	6	10.79%	6	11.79%	6	low
FC-04	26.07%	2	24.50%	1	24.23%	1	24.03%	1	23.68%	1	high
FC-05	26.12%	1	20.30%	2	19.27%	2	18.46%	2	16.90%	2	high
FC-06	12.14%	4	15.03%	4	15.41%	4	15.53%	4	15.26%	5	med

6.2 Sub-systems Design

The set of KPIs whose values significantly alter the behaviour of each Rs will be selected. They are those KPIs that really define the behaviour for each Capital due to their great influence where others converge in a given period of action (holistic criteria: global variation greater than 50% by registration throughout the 5 monitoring campaigns on a mutual interaction time-lapse: Figure 2). The advantages of saving effort and time this method provides are obvious for the modelling of the Rs' behaviour.

Figure 2: Variation criteria for KPI selection (© RURITAGE).

Hence the GPI is recalculated using only the KPIs that meet the selection criteria (so called ReKPI²). If the value obtained this time for the GPI (renamed ReGPI) is at least ¾ of the initial value (considering all the possible KPIs), then it can be reasonably inferred that the aspects represented by the ReKPIs are the levers on which to carry out the actions corresponding to the SIA in question (Figure 3). Otherwise, all KPIs should be considered as 'levers' (alternatively, it could be played with different KPI to meet the ¾ criterion -finding all possible / most suitable combinations-). KPIs meaning serves to accordingly feedback the actions that are being deployed in the rural area. The effect time is the one that corresponds to the delay in its appearance.

² Relevant KPI

Figure 3: Foundations considered for SD modelling (example with Cultural Capital - Geopark Karavanke/Karawanken) (© RURITAGE).

6.2.1 The Matrix of KPIs – SIAs

The matrix of KPIs and SIAs assignment relates both concepts in a series of tables (from ¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia. to ¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.). The initial list of KPIs is too long, so it is better to focus only on those indicators where the information is, following priorities decided by the domain experts, as shown previously with the OWA analysis, and the validation criteria for KPI selection. Once we have the list of KPIs and SIAs, the matrix can be built.

In the points where a SIA and a KPI cross, the cells are highlighted if enough data coming from monitoring is available. Whenever the data are considered relevant according to the criteria previously stated, a brief narrative explaining how both are related is placed, and those are the seeds for building the SD models described in the next section.

Table 9: Cultural Capital KPI-SIA assignment.

			SIA					
Code	OWA Relevance		Pilgrimage	Local Food	Migration	Arts&Festivals	Resilience	Landscape
Cultural Capital	CC-01	High						
	CC-02	Med						
	CC-03	Low				Social Media		
	CC-04	Low						
	CC-05	Low						
	CC-06a	High						
	CC-06b	High	Cultural Events		Cultural Events	Cultural Events	Cultural Events	Cultural Events
	CC-07	Med						
	CC-08	Med		Traditional Skills	Traditional Skills		Traditional Skills	Traditional Skills
	CC-09	Med						
CC-10	Med	Tourism	Tourism		Tourism		Tourism	

Table 10: Natural Capital KPI-SIA assignment.

		SIA						
Code	OWA Relevance	Pilgrimage	Local Food	Migration	Arts&Festivals	Resilience	Landscape	
Natural Capital	NC-01	High						
	NC-02a	Low						
	NC-02b	Med				Protected Areas	Protected Areas	
	NC-03	Low						
	NC-04	Med						
	NC-05	Low	Sustainable Certifis and Labelling					
	NC-06	High	Local Products	Local Products				
NC-07	High		Green Tourism Packages				Green Tourism Packages	

Table 11: Built Capital KPI-SIA assignment.

		SIA						
Code	OWA Relevance	Pilgrimage	Local Food	Migration	Arts&Festivals	Resilience	Landscape	
Built Capital	BC-01	Low						
	BC-02	Low						
	BC-03	Low	Pol (Points of Interes)				Pol (Points of Interes)	
	BC-04	Low						
	BC-05	Low		Restaurants				
	BC-06	High						
	BC-07	High					Cycle/Hiking Paths	
	BC-08	High						
	BC-09	Med						
	BC-10	Med						
	BC-11	Med	Restored/Reused Buildings		Restored/Reused Buildings		Restored/Reused Buildings	Restored/Reused Buildings
	BC-12	High						
	BC-13	Med						
	BC-14	Med	Fairs and Tourism Events	Fairs Promotion Area		Fairs Promotion Area		
	BC-15a	High				Signals and Panels	Signals and Panels	Signals and Panels
BC-15b	Med							

Table 12: Social Capital KPI-SIA assignment.

		SIA					
Code	OWA Relevance	Pilgrimage	Local Food	Migration	Arts&Festivals	Resilience	Landscape
Social Capital	SC-01a	High		Citizen Engagement Activities	Citizen Engagement Activities	Citizen Engagement Activities	Citizen Engagement Activities
	SC-01b	High					
	SC-02	High	Stakeholders	Stakeholders	Stakeholders	Stakeholders	Stakeholders
	SC-03	Med		Local Associations			Local Associations
	SC-04	Med					Voluntary Activities
	SC-05a	Low			Projects Addressing Migrants		
	SC-05b	Med					
	SC-06a	Low					
	SC-06b	Low					
SC-07	Med				Disadvantaged People Engaged		

Table 13: Human Capital KPI-SIA assignment.

		SIA					
Code	OWA Relevance	Pilgrimage	Local Food	Migration	Arts&Festivals	Resilience	Landscape
Human Capital	HC-01	High					
	HC-02	Low		Leisure Facilities/Events	Leisure Facilities/Events		Leisure Facilities/Events
	HC-03	Med		Migrants Educational Programs			
	HC-04	Med					
	HC-05	High	Self-Employment			Self-Employment	
	HC-06	Low				Student Internships	
	HC-07	High	Learning	Learning			Learning
	HC-08	Med					
	HC-09	Low					

Table 14: Financial Capital KPI-SIA assignment.

		SIA					
Code	OWA Relevance	Pilgrimage	Local Food	Migration	Arts&Festivals	Resilience	Landscape
Financial Capital	FC-01	Low				Tourist Accommodation	Tourist Accommodation
	FC-02	Med					
	FC-03	Low				PPPs Signed	PPPs Signed
	FC-04	High					
	FC-05	High		Start-Ups			
	FC-06	Med					New Business Models

6.3 System Design and SD Model Architecture

The completed matrix leads to the high-level model. This model is meant to be a very intuitive construction relating SIAs and KPIs. It can be built up of small pieces or just in bigger ones, containing more than one relation. In RURITAGE we have opted for building independent big models, one by SIA, due to the particularities of each case. This way, it is also possible to fine-tune the models, when additional information from new Replicators would be available.

The flows (wide arrows) contain the information obtained from the data provided by the pilots through the 2.5 years of monitoring, which are properly combined into the stocks (boxes). Other auxiliary elements (circles) serve to set the targets or the weights, and the relations between those elements are drawn with thin arrows. Modifying all these parameters and the formulas into the flows is it possible to adjust the behaviour of the model, as explained later in this section. The series of figures, from Figure 4 to Figure 9, show the SD models for any of the SIAs.

Figure 4: SD model for Pilgrimage SIA (© RURITAGE).

Figure 5: SD model for Local Food SIA (© RURITAGE).

Figure 6: SD model for Migration SIA (© RURITAGE).

Figure 7: SD model for Art & Festivals SIA (© RURITAGE).

Figure 8: SD model for Resilience SIA (© RURITAGE).

Figure 9: SD model for Landscape management SIA (© RURITAGE).

All these SD models have been integrated into the RURITAGE Monitoring Platform. The user interface (see Figure 10) developed for the end-users provide the necessary elements to use the model. First, it is necessary to select the right SIA, in the top-most part of the screen. This way, the adequate SD base model is displayed. The user should set the size of the Replicator that is going to be modelled by introducing the population and the area in square kilometres in the corresponding input fields. Then, a base estimation is shown in the budget and Capitals/KPIs charts. At the beginning of the simulation all the gears, or knobs, are set to 50 by default, but the user can modify their value in the range between 0 and 100, 0 meaning no actions will be developed in that field and 100 meaning the Replicators wants to develop that field to its full potential. Playing with the different knobs allows the user to lay out different *what-if* scenarios and get an estimation of the development level after some months, and the associated cost.

A full description of the functioning of SD models simulation and the results can be found in the User Manual (available online, in the Monitoring landing page inside the RURITAGE Ecosystem³) and in the deliverable D4.4, respectively.

³ <https://ruritage-ecosystem.eu/kpi>

Figure 10: SD model integrated into the Monitoring Platform (© RURITAGE).

7. Conclusions

This report summarises the process that has been followed to build the different SD models, one by SIA. The demonstrator application along with the SD models published in the Monitoring Platform will become the key show cases for the use of SD modelling in heritage-led rural regeneration processes and thus instrumental to gain an audience that is willing to listen and adopt the solutions within the project consortium and beyond. The proposed solution is meant to demonstrate the potential of making SD modelling available as Software as a Service (SaaS) to be integrated into existing decision support systems used by planners and foresight experts.

Key performance indicators can be a valuable tool for establishing future rural strategies, as well as for evaluating development action plan impacts. However, nowadays, no standard has been developed for evaluating heritage-led practices in rural areas and there is no broadly-accepted indicator system which integrates the systemic innovation areas of RURITAGE as a framework to identify unique CNH potential within rural communities. As a result, a tailored procedure has been established in order to define the KPIs which would take part in a reliable evaluation plan and SD modelling.

The monitoring platform shows from global performance values (GPI) to detailed KPI data through spider or radar charts and data tables, in addition to the SD models and user interface to set out and simulate possible *what-if* scenarios. This would help local stakeholders and public authorities to make better informed decisions to definitively boost rural areas over CNH as primary resources.

The feedback from the six rural areas that have been testing the functioning of the platform will allow further improvements and fine-tuning of the SD models, going deeper into the analysis of feedback loops and time delays that affect model behaviour over time.

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